

Genome sequences of bacterial biocontrol agents isolated from *Solanum lycopersicum* and *Medicago truncatula* in Tunisia

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Abstract

The whole-genomes shotgun sequences of 6 bacterial biocontrol agents isolated from *Medicago truncatula* and *Solanum lycopersicum* collected in the North of Tunisia are presented in this study. The genome sequences supplement the existing genomics resources and give us an insight into the biodiversity of bacteria associated with plants and prospect key genes required for their endophytic behaviour, interactions with their hosts and biocontrol activity traits against plant pathogens.

Introduction

Endophytic bacteria are mutualistic microorganisms that spend most of their life cycle within the plant tissues without causing any visible damage to their host, and they have been found to colonize the majority of plant species (Hallmann et al. 1997; Truyens et al. 2015). Thus, an endophyte-free plant is a rare exception in nature (Partida-Martínez and Heil, 2011). Endophytic bacteria affect plant growth directly or indirectly. Direct promotion of plant growth occurs by facilitating the acquisition of environmental resources including nitrogen, phosphorus and iron as well as modulating plant growth by providing or regulating various hormones plants, especially auxin, cytokinins or ethylene (Glick, 2015; Conrath et al., 2015). Endophytic bacteria indirectly promote plant growth by adapting their host to various environmental stresses, and they are also known to strengthen plant immune systems by inducing resistance against various plant pathogens (Santoyo et al., 2016; Vaishnav et al. 2018).

The plant species has a strong influence on the type of endophytic community it harbour (Ding and Melcher, 2016). Indeed, it has been found that endophytic diversity varies greatly among plant species growing in the same soil (Afzal et al., 2019). In general, Proteobacteria is the most common phylum isolated from plants, consisting of the classes α -, β -, and γ -Proteobacteria, with γ -Proteobacteria being the most diverse and dominant (Miliute et al., 2015 ; Santoyo et al., 2016). The prevalence of these phyla however may vary depending on the host plant type (Bodenhausen et al., 2013). *Bacillus*, *Burkholderia*, *Microbacterium*, *Pantoea*, *Pseudomonas* and *Stenotrophomonas* are among the more common isolated genera, with *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* are the predominant ones (Chaturvedi et al., 2016).

Cultivation-independent approaches based on marker gene profiling or shotgun metagenome sequencing have greatly enhanced our understanding of plant microbial interactions (Bulgarelli et al., 2012; Ofek-Lalzar et al., 2014). Complete genome and plasmid sequences of endophytic bacteria in different plants were previously reported (Han et al., 2011; Leontidou et al., 2020; Samaras et al., 2021; Leal et al., 2021). The most important high-throughput approach is whole genome sequencing of the endophytic bacteria and the host plant, which reveals all genes in an endophytic bacterium and their predicted function, allowing one to predict potential mutual benefits between the plant and the endophytic bacterium. Endophytic bacteria's genomes encode for all necessary genes required for their endophytic nature and survival inside hosts (Sheibani-Tezerji et al. 2015). Therefore, studying these genomes using computational tools allows a rapid understanding of their genes to explore their multi-bioactive mechanisms inside their host.

Six endophytic bacteria isolates from two model plants *Medicago truncatula* and *Solanum lycopersicum* in Tunisia were used in this study. In a previous work, the TR1 and DHFL4 strains were selected because they showed antifungal activities and protected *S. lycopersicum* against *Botrytis cinerea* via producing volatile organic compounds (Chaouachi et al., 2021). In another work, a consortium composed by four bacterial strains i.e. BF25-1, BF25-2, BF25-3, BF25-4 was selected because it induced resistance mechanisms in *M. truncatula* against *Phoma medicaginis* and *Verticillium alfalfae* (Chaouachi, 2021). The identification of these isolates was previously done using the 16S RNA gene (Chaouachi et al., 2021). However, in this complementary study we describe the Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) of these bacterial strains which has several advantages over the 16S rRNA

identification method, including improved detection of bacterial species, increased detection of diversity, and improved functional gene prediction (Ranjan and al., 2016).

Material and Methods

Bacterial isolates

TR1 and DHFL4 strains were isolated from roots and flowers of *S.lycopersicum* cultivated in CapBon region (Chaouachi et al., 2021) and BF25 consortium strains were isolated from leaves of *M.truncatula* in Bulla-Regia region (Chaouachi, 2021) in Tunisia. Bacterial strains were isolated according to the procedure described by Chaouachi et al. (2021).

Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA

Bacterial culturing, DNA extraction, genome sequencing and assembly were conducted by microbesNG according to their protocols <https://microbesng.com/>. Genomic DNA sequences from the bacterial isolates were acquired using a sequencing service provider named MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK, <https://microbesng.com>). A protocol supplied by MicrobesNG was followed to ship the bacterial samples.

The reads were trimmed using Trimmomatic version 0.39 (Bolger et al., 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15 and the quality was assessed using in-house scripts combined with Samtools version 1.4 ([git://github.com/samtools/samtools.git](https://github.com/samtools/samtools.git)), BedTools version 2.18 (Quinlan and Hall, 2010) and bwa-mem (Li and Durbin, 2009) software. Sequence reads were assembled into contigs using Quast software version 5.0.2 (Gurevich et al., 2013). The genomes were annotated with Prokka 1.14.3 (<https://github.com/tseemann/prokka>), protein coding features and tRNA were predicted using Prodigal version 2.6 (Hyatt et al., 2010) and rRNA was predicted by ARAGORN version 1.2 (Laslett and Canback, 2004).

Results

We sequenced the genomes of six bacterial biocontrol agents isolated from *S. lycopersicum* and *M. truncatula* (Chaouachi et al., 2021; Chaouachi, 2021). The sequence reads assembled by Quast revealed a number of contigs ranging from 34 to 185 with the largest contigs of 2082069 bp. The contigs of the genome assemblies of our six strains TR1, DHFL4, BF25-1, BF25-2, BF25-3 and BF25-4 add up to 4,445,353 bp ; 4,088,028 bp ;

4,181,732 bp ; 4,167,797 bp ; 4,168,616 bp and 4,171,782 bp respectively. The GC contents of the genomes of these bacterial strains are 66.58 %, 43.83 %, 46.18 %, 46.20 %, 46.20 % and 46.19 %, for TR1, DHFL4, BF25-1, BF25-2, BF25-3 and BF25-4 strains respectively. The total number of genes including the protein-coding genes, tRNA and tmRNA genes for each isolate is listed in Table 1. The results based on the ANI test and current taxonomic nomenclature revealed an identity over 98 % of the submitted genome sequence to *Bacillus* and *Stenotrophomonas* genera. The sequence of TR1 genome is 94.86 % identical to the type genome of *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*. The sequence DHFL4 is 99 % identical the type genome of *B. subtilis subsp. stercoris*. The genomes sequences of BF25-1, BF25-2, BF25-3 and BF25-4 are identical to *Bacillus* species type genomes with low identity to *B. licheniformis* species.

Data availability

This whole-genome shotgun has been deposited at DDBJ/ENA/GenBank under accession numbers JAJCTJ000000000, JAJCTK000000000, JAJCTL000000000, JAJCTM000000000, JAJCUA000000000 and JAJCTN000000000. The versions described in this paper are JAJCTJ010000000, JAJCTK010000000, JAJCTL010000000, JAJCTM010000000, JAJCUA010000000 and JAJCTN010000000. Raw sequence reads have been deposited in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive under BioProject number [PRJNA761700](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA761700) and run numbers [SRR15810706](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR15810706), [SRR15928477](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR15928477), [SRR15928504](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR15928504), [SRR15928505](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR15928505), [SRR15928554](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR15928554) and [SRR15928555](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR15928555).

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are being shared prior to formal publication and should be considered preliminary. We encourage and welcome feedback from the community. Please get in touch with ND (dnaceur2014@gmail.com) for more information.

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Table 1. Summary statistics for biocontrol agents' genomes assembled from Illumina reads.

Bacterial strain	Host plant	Biosample	# contigs ≥ 1000 bp	Largest contig	Total length	GC (%)	Mean coverage	N50	CDS	tRNA	tmRNA	GenBank Accession (Assembly)	GenBank Accession (Raw reads)
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> BF25-1	<i>Medicago truncatula</i>	SAMN213 58417	25	664416	418173 2	46.1 8	72.5583	3925 87	4279	79	1	JAJCTJ000000	SRR158107 06
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> BF25-2	<i>Medicago truncatula</i>	SAMN214 67401	27	664416	416779 7	46.2 0	42.6586	3925 89	4242	79	1	JAJCTK000000	SRR159284 77
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> BF25-3	<i>Medicago truncatula</i>	SAMN214 67574	24	664416	416861 6	46.2 0	49.038	3925 89	4249	79	1	JAJCTL000000	SRR159285 04
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> BF25-4	<i>Medicago truncatula</i>	SAMN214 67662	25	664416	417178 2	46.1 9	74.338	3925 89	4253	79	1	JAJCTM000000	SRR159285 05
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> subsp <i>stercoris</i> DHFL4	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	SAMN214 67678	9	208206 9	408802 8	43.8 3	128.097	2082 069	4010	85	1	JAJCUA000000	SRR159285 54
<i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i> TR1	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	SAMN214 67686	53	372606	444535 3	66.5 8	61.2958	1584 97	3998	71	1	JAJCTN000000	SRR159285 55

References

- Afzal, I., Shinwari, Z. K., Sikandar, S., Shahzad, S. (2019). Plant beneficial endophytic bacteria: mechanisms, diversity, host range and genetic determinants. *Microbiological research*, 221, 36-49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2019.02.001>
- Bodenhausen, N., Horton, M. W., Bergelson, J. (2013). Bacterial communities associated with the leaves and the roots of *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *PloS one*, 8(2), e56329. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0056329>
- Bolger, A. M., Lohse, M., Usadel, B. (2014). Trimmomatic: a flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence data. *Bioinformatics*, 30(15), 2114-2120. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu170>
- Bulgarelli, D., Rott, M., Schlaeppi, K., van Themaat, E. V. L., Ahmadinejad, N., Assenza, F., ... Schulze-Lefert, P. (2012). Revealing structure and assembly cues for *Arabidopsis* root-inhabiting bacterial microbiota. *Nature*, 488 (7409), 91-95. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11336>
- Chaouachi, M., Marzouk, T., Jallouli, S., Elkahoui, S., Gentzbittel, L., Ben, C., Djébali, N. (2021). Activity assessment of tomato endophytic bacteria bioactive compounds for the postharvest biocontrol of *Botrytis cinerea*. *Postharvest Biology and Technology*, 172, 111389. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.postharvbio.2020.111389>
- Chaouachi, M. (2021). Plant immunization with biological elicitors: Study of mechanisms and characterization of molecules [non published doctoral thesis under joint-supervision], University of Tunis El Manar and University of Toulouse.
- Chaturvedi, H., Singh, V., Gupta, G. (2016). Potential of bacterial endophytes as plant growth promoting factors. *J Plant Pathol Microbiol*, 7(9), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2157-7471.1000376>
- Conrath, U., Beckers, G. J., Langenbach, C. J., & Jaskiewicz, M. R. (2015). Priming for enhanced defense. *Annual review of phytopathology*, 53, 97-119. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-phyto-080614-120132>

Ding, T., Melcher, U. (2016). Influences of plant species, season and location on leaf endophytic bacterial communities of non-cultivated plants. *PloS one*, *11*(3), e0150895. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0150895>

Glick, B. R. (2015). *Beneficial plant-bacterial interactions* (pp. 1-28). Heidelberg: Springer.

Gurevich, A., Saveliev, V., Vyahhi, N., Tesler, G. (2013). QUASt: quality assessment tool for genome assemblies. *Bioinformatics*, *29*(8), 1072-1075. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-44368-9>

Hallmann, J., Quadt-Hallmann, A., Mahaffee, W. F., Kloepper, J. W. (1997). Bacterial endophytes in agricultural crops. *Canadian journal of microbiology*, *43*(10), 895-914. <https://doi.org/10.1139/m97-131>

Han, J. I., Choi, H. K., Lee, S. W., Orwin, P. M., Kim, J., LaRoe, S. L., ... Han, C. (2011). Complete genome sequence of the metabolically versatile plant growth-promoting endophyte *Variovorax paradoxus* S110. *Journal of bacteriology*, *193*(5), 1183-1190. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JB.00925-10>

Hyatt, D., Chen, G. L., LoCascio, P. F., Land, M. L., Larimer, F. W., Hauser, L. J. (2010). Prodigal: prokaryotic gene recognition and translation initiation site identification. *BMC bioinformatics*, *11*(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-11-119>

Laslett, D., Canback, B. (2004). ARAGORN, a program to detect tRNA genes and tmRNA genes in nucleotide sequences. *Nucleic acids research*, *32*(1), 11-16. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkh152>

Leal, C., Fontaine, F., Aziz, A., Egas, C., Clément, C., Trotel-Aziz, P. (2021). Genome sequence analysis of the beneficial *Bacillus subtilis* PTA-271 isolated from a *Vitis vinifera* (cv. Chardonnay) rhizospheric soil: assets for sustainable biocontrol. *Environmental microbiome*, *16*(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40793-021-00372-3>

Leontidou, K., Genitsaris, S., Papadopoulou, A., Kamou, N., Bosmali, I., Matsi, T., ... Mellidou, I. (2020). Plant growth promoting rhizobacteria isolated from halophytes and drought-tolerant plants: genomic characterisation and exploration of phyto-beneficial traits. *Scientific reports*, *10*(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-71652-0>

- Li, H., Durbin, R. (2009). Fast and accurate short read alignment with Burrows–Wheeler transform. *bioinformatics*, 25(14), 1754-1760. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btp324>
- Miliute, I., Buzaitė, O., Baniulis, D., Stanys, V. (2015). Bacterial endophytes in agricultural crops and their role in stress tolerance: a review. *Zemdirbyste-Agriculture*, 102(4), 465-478. <https://doi.org/10.13080/z-a.2015.102.060>
- Ofek-Lalzar, M., Sela, N., Goldman-Voronov, M., Green, S. J., Hadar, Y., Minz, D. (2014). Niche and host-associated functional signatures of the root surface microbiome. *Nature communications*, 5(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms5950>
- Partida-Martinez, L. P. P., Heil, M. (2011). The microbe-free plant: fact or artifact?. *Frontiers in plant science*, 2, 100. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2011.00100>
- Quinlan, A. R., Hall, I. M. (2010). BEDTools: a flexible suite of utilities for comparing genomic features. *Bioinformatics*, 26(6), 841-842. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btq033>
- Ranjan, R., Rani, A., Metwally, A., McGee, H. S., Perkins, D. L. (2016). Analysis of the microbiome: Advantages of whole genome shotgun versus 16S amplicon sequencing. *Biochemical and biophysical research communications*, 469(4), 967-977. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2015.12.083>
- Samaras, A., Nikolaidis, M., Antequera-Gómez, M. L., Cámara-Almirón, J., Romero, D., Moschakis, T., ... Karaoglanidis, G. S. (2021). Whole genome sequencing and root colonization studies reveal novel insights in the biocontrol potential and growth promotion by *Bacillus subtilis* MBI 600 on cucumber. *Frontiers in microbiology*, 3437. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.600393>
- Santoyo, G., Moreno-Hagelsieb, G., del Carmen Orozco-Mosqueda, M., Glick, B. R. (2016). Plant growth-promoting bacterial endophytes. *Microbiological research*, 183, 92-99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2015.11.008>
- Sheibani-Tezerji, R., Naveed, M., Jehl, M. A., Sessitsch, A., Rattei, T., Mitter, B. (2015). The genomes of closely related *Pantoea ananatis* maize seed endophytes having different effects on the host plant differ in secretion system genes and mobile genetic elements. *Frontiers in microbiology*, 6, 440. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2015.00440>

Truyens, S., Weyens, N., Cuypers, A., Vangronsveld, J. (2015). Bacterial seed endophytes: genera, vertical transmission and interaction with plants. *Environmental Microbiology Reports*, 7(1), 40-50. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1758-2229.12181>

Vaishnav, A., Shukla, A. K., Sharma, A., Kumar, R., Choudhary, D. K. (2019). Endophytic bacteria in plant salt stress tolerance: current and future prospects. *Journal of Plant Growth Regulation*, 38(2), 650-668. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00344-018-9880-1>